

PREPRINT

Collaboration in Education Research from Africa

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Acknowledgements

This work is part of the COMPARE project (REF: PID2020-117007RA-I00) funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science (MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033). Nicolas Robinson-Garcia is funded by a Ramón y Cajal grant from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (REF: RYC2019-027886-I) and Elvira González-Salmón is currently supported by an FPU grant from the Spanish Ministry of Science (Ref: FPU2021/02320).

Declaration of Interest statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest in conducting or publishing this research.

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Data statement

The data used in the analysis presented in this article is publicly available at <https://zenodo.org/records/1464561>

1. Introduction

Modern science has for a long time been regarded as a collective and public endeavour (Eamon, 1985). There is also the expectation that research should, at least in part, display patterns of local *and* international research to become more relevant and significant to society (Altbach, 2008). This expectation finds expression in national policies and in research funding regimes. Universities and their researchers in developing countries where the expectation for a close relationship between knowledge production and development is most pressing (Cloete et al., 2012), must simultaneously align themselves with, on the one hand, the norms of global science and the agendas of international funding agencies and, on the other hand, with national policy expectations (Marginson, 2022; Muller et al. 2017; Wagner, 2008).

Globally, the rate of international scientific collaboration rose from 22% in 2015 to 24% in 2019 (UNESCO, 2021). While one might expect international collaboration networks to exhibit a modular structure driven by specialization clusters in an equitable scientific landscape, the reality is more akin to a hierarchical structure (Miao et al., 2022). In this hierarchy, countries with higher scientific capacity take on leading roles, directing and shaping the international scientific agenda (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2018; Miao et al., 2024; Samuel, 2024). Leydesdorff and Wagner (2008) posited that the global network reinforces a core group of countries with strong national science systems, arguing that peripheral countries could be disadvantaged by increased strength at the core. In other words, growing collaboration at a global scale nests historical inequalities, particularly asymmetries between the global scientific centre (or core) and the periphery (Collyer, 2018).

Africa's world share of publications grew from 1.5% in 2005 to 2.8% in 2015 (Mouton & Blanckenberg, 2018). The growth is explained, in part, by an increase in the participation of African scholars in international networks (Confraria & Godinho, 2015). In the period 2015 to 2021, co-authorships between researchers at 16 African universities and their international counterparts ranged from a low of 43% (University of Lagos) to a high of 89% (University of Rwanda) (ARUA, 2022). However, there has been a growing concern for African countries to assert their own research agendas and interests when collaborating internationally (Holmarsdóttir et al., 2013; Samuel, 2024). The generally held perception that by increasing international collaboration networks, national scientific systems can be revitalised or reinforced (e.g., Eduan, 2019) has increasingly been challenged in recent years (e.g., Odeny & Bosurgi, 2022; Robinson-Garcia & Ràfols, 2019), introducing the idea that differing collaboration networks may be driven by conflicting interests between being part of the global agenda and responding to local needs (Robinson-Garcia, Woolley & Costas, 2019).

In this paper we explore the role of international collaboration dynamics of African researchers in the field of education, as a scientific discipline that is exposed to and operating within the expectations and pressures of global discourses, institutionalised norms and national priorities. Collaboration emerges from epistemological connections which, in turn, materialise in the form of stronger or weaker concentrations of research in particular areas of interest as well as within and across national borders. We explore the extent to which the distribution of power and resources within global research networks shapes international collaboration on the continent. To do so, we use an extensive and comprehensive dataset of research publications extracted from the bibliographic database OpenAlex.

2. Literature review

2.1 International collaboration networks

The study of research collaboration has been one of the recurring topics for both bibliometricians and sociologists of science. Beaver and Rosen (1978) and Crane (1972) developed the foundations on research collaboration dynamics in the 1970s, and since then many studies have been devoted to understanding how collaboration networks operate (Newman, 2001), connect researchers and fields (Granovetter, 1983) or affect scientific impact (Bote et al., 2013; van Raan, 1998), among others. At a structural level, international networks follow a hierarchical structure (Wagner et al., 2017), with a negative relationship between the geographical spread of the network and the share of collaborative publications (Wagner, 2005). Furthermore, there are crucial distinctions in the type of international networks and the research orientation of their collective endeavours.

Robinson-Garcia, Woolley and Costas (2019) used the distinction made by De Lange and Glänzel between bilateral, multilateral and no collaboration (De Lange & Glänzel, 1997; Glänzel & De Lange, 1997) to analyze the topic similarity between these three categories and found a heterogeneous picture by region and country in terms of the internal similarity of topics. This finding, they suggest, could point towards differing collaboration dynamics and strategies. These dynamics were clearly characterized for East and South Asian countries where distinct disciplinary country profiles based on the type of international collaboration were found (Woolley et al., 2017).

In the case of developing countries, there is a commonly held belief that international collaboration is a positive strategy to improve scientific visibility and impact (Quan et al., 2019). However, at least in Africa, there are some concerns regarding the role these collaborative efforts play (Confraria et al., 2017; Robinson-Garcia & Ràfols, 2019). This includes the relatively weak positions these countries occupy when compared to countries with higher research capacities (Leydesdorff & Wagner, 2008), resulting in asymmetrical collaborations (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2018; Feld & Kreimer, 2019).

A study by Vieira (2022) has shown that publications on the topic of the collaboration and contributions of African researchers has increased. Findings show, however, that few African countries have researched the topic, a third of the publications were written exclusively by African researchers, and the topic has high visibility. The analysis revealed that driving factors, effects, patterns, networks and asymmetries concerning the international research collaboration of researchers in Africa were the main themes researched.

2.2 The role of author order and the allocation of contributions

These power dynamics can be easily traced through an analysis of the authorship of scientific publication and of the order in which authors are listed in those publications (Bhandari et al., 2014). Author position has traditionally been used as a proxy for attributing credit and prestige among researchers (Merton, 1973). In this sense, most scientific fields follow a U-shape to distribute credit based on author order (Bhandari, et al., 2004; Costas & Bordons, 2011; Larivière et al., 2016), that is, while first and last authors will be considered to have contributed extensively to a publication, middle authors will be attributed with lesser credit (Mongeon et al., 2017). Within first and last author positions, further differences can be established, as last authors will tend to be senior scholars, while first authorship will be devoted to younger scholars (Escabias & Robinson-Garcia, 2022), revealing a mix between seniority and task distribution influencing the author byline (Sauermaann & Haeussler, 2017). Little is known about the relative contributions of middle authors (Larivière et al., 2016).

In a previous study using bibliographic data retrieved from the Scopus database [van Schalkwyk et al., 2024], we analyzed differences in author position of African scholars considering their career length (based on when they published their first publication) and the type of collaboration (we distinguished between international collaboration within and outside the continent), analyzing differences between African scholars based on their mobility experience. This study showed that African scholars tend to occupy leading positions (first or last author) in around 30% of their publications when collaborating internationally. However, the study lacked a benchmark to make comparisons with other countries or scientific fields which may account for differences.

International research collaboration may either ameliorate or entrench epistemological inequalities within international research collaboration. Kreimer and Zabala (2008) show how

centre–periphery collaborations position scholars from the centre as primary knowledge producers, while scholars from the periphery are relegated to ‘sub-contractors’, producing knowledge that does not relate to local problems. Meleka et al. (2019) examined global research collaborations in community health worker programs and found that knowledge production flows predominantly through a pool of connected high-income country authors and North-South collaborations. The ‘introversion’ of American and European science further contributes to the exclusion of science from the scientific periphery (Collyer, 2018). This perpetuates ‘an unstated but real global division of intellectual labour’ (Baber, 2003: 621).

Alatas (2003) argues that theoretical and methodological innovations are considered legitimate tasks for scholars from the scientific centre while fieldwork and data collection are the designated roles for those in the periphery. The practice of scientists from wealthy nations visiting lower-income countries, collecting samples, publishing the results with little or no involvement from local scientists, and providing no benefit for the local community is often referred to as “neo-colonial”, “helicopter”, or “parachute” research. In one study, it was found that 70% of articles in a random sample of publications about least-developed countries did not include a local research co-author (Dahdouh-Guebas et al., 2003). More recent research on global health in sub-Saharan Africa, found that 13.5% of all papers had no local co-authors (Hedt-Gauthier et al., 2019).

The field of educational research in Africa is no exception to the prevailing power dynamics at play in global science, and the epistemological disparities and anxieties this causes among researchers working in the field of education research in Africa. As Samuel (2024, 233) writes: “the terrain of educational research is embedded within contestations and possibilities of collaborative efforts across many interlocuting partners both at the systemic macro-level and at the micro- and meso-level”. Still writing from the vantage point of education research, Samuel (2024, 253) goes further:

when research borrows uncritically from beyond its borders, it runs the risk of elevating and reinforcing the source of the theorists from elsewhere, and undercuts the potential of activating relevant, appropriate and worthwhile questions and analyses from within the local context. This kind of critical distance ... constitutes working beyond saviour research where the solutions to current challenges are drawn through lenses not circumscribed by deference to saviours who aim to proliferate their products in evangelical ways. This does not mean that one does not examine the patterns and perspectives of others for their potential value. Instead, a critical research stance critiques the embedded external hegemonic discourse as well as one’s own valuing and belief systems.

This paper is a descriptive bibliometric study that aims to explore the available evidence regarding the collaboration patterns of education researchers in Africa as well their relative contributions to research over time. It is therefore primarily a data-led mapping of collaboration patterns in the field of education, the findings of which will inform whether there are changes in the prevailing asymmetries between the global centre (core) and the scientific periphery.

To operationalize our research interest we posed the following two research questions: How do researchers from Africa in the field of education collaborate as exemplified by their (co-)authorship of scientific publications? Does the contribution of researchers from Africa in the field of education change over time as exemplified by their authorship position in co-authored scientific publications?

3. Methods

The approach of the research presented in this article is that of a (quantitative) bibliometric analysis. We conducted a trend analysis along with descriptive comparative analysis to provide an empirical overview of the author-level collaborations and contributions in the field of education with a specific focus on researchers based in Africa.

To answer our research questions, we therefore limit our focus to the African continent and to the field of education research by relying on a large dataset of publications between 2000 and 2024 indexed in OpenAlex. All years are full years with the exception of 2024 which is a partial year of 10 months (January to October). We elected to include the partial year as it represents the most recent data available and while the year 2024 may not be comparable with previous years, comparisons between 2024 publications is possible. We focused exclusively on journal articles given the observation of the “articlisation” of science (Beigel et al., 2025; Paye & Renisio, 2017) and that quality metadata are more readily available for journal articles than for other publication types such as monographs, book chapters and conference papers. The data are openly accessible at <https://zenodo.org/records/14645615>.

We selected OpenAlex as our data source because (1) existing work has shown that OpenAlex usually outperforms other databases in terms of general coverage (Alperin et al., 2024; Culbert et al., 2024; Gusenbauer, 2024; Jiao et al., 2023) and (2) it provides the best coverage of publications from Africa, including the richest metadata for publications by researchers based in Africa (Alonso-Álvarez & van Eck, 2024). We accessed OpenAlex data hosted by the Insyspo project at the University of Campinas (Brazil) using Google Big Query (Insyspo, 2024). After cleaning the data and filtering by year (January 2000 to October 2024), country (African countries) and topic (Education topics), we found 91,173 unique African authors and 89,293 unique publications.

We found several cases of double affiliations for authors. We chose to delete those papers for which there was at least one author affiliated with institutions in multiple countries (803 unique papers), and this resulted in 90,380 unique African authors and 88,490 unique articles. If we include non-Africa-based collaborators, there are a total of 112,585 authors. When an author had multiple affiliations from the same country, we counted it only once for that country.

While it does not address directly any of our two research questions, we deemed it necessary to provide as background a continent-wide overview of publication trends in the field of education. To calculate the number of publications per African country per year in the field of education for which at least one author is affiliated with an organisation in Africa (Table 2 and Table A1 in Annexure A), we used the data from OpenAlex, filtered by topic, country and year, and we grouped the results by country and year.

To calculate collaborations in the field of education by location for co-authors relative to authors from Africa (Figures 1a and 1b), we included all papers for which at least one author is affiliated with an organisation in Africa (for the topic “education” from 2000 to 2023). We then divided the papers into four groups: (1) no collaboration (single author), (2) institutional collaboration (more than one author from the same institution), (3) national collaboration (more than one author from more than one institution in the same country), and (4) international collaboration (more than one author from more than one country) (see Table 1). No single paper could be allocated to more than one of the four categories.

Table 1: Number of papers per collaboration type, 2000-2024

Type of collaboration	No collaboration	Institutional collaboration	National collaboration	International collaboration	Total
Number of education articles	40 086	23 572	8 032	16 800	88 490

To refine our classification of international collaboration we created two subgroups consisting of (1) core national science systems (i.e. those countries that are well-resourced in terms of investment in research) and (2) peripheral national science systems (i.e. those countries less well-resourced in terms of their science systems). This approach distinguishes our study from most other studies that typically categorize international research as collaboration between research from Africa with researchers from anywhere in the world outside of the continent. Not only does this more common approach treat Africa as a single country effectively disregarding regional- and country-level differences (Adams et al., 2014), but it fails to take into account the resource and concomitant power asymmetries prevalent at the global level (and even with high unequal national science systems). While still a relatively crude categorisation, we therefore regard the core-periphery categorisation as a more realistic one than an Africa versus rest-of-the-world categorisation.

To operationalise the distinction between core and peripheral national science systems, we assume that gross expenditure on research and development (GERD) as a percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) serves as a robust and internationally comparable proxy indicating the financial resource richness of a national science system. We calculated the 20-year world average (2004-2023) for GERD as a percent of GDP using UNESCO UIS data to arrive at a GERD of 1.69% (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2024). We then calculated the 20-year average GERD as a percentage of GDP per country and created a list of all countries that have spent on average more than 1.69% of GDP on R&D over the past 20 years (i.e. “core countries”). This produced a list of 22 countries (see Table A2 in Appendix 1).

The position of authors for co-authored papers in OpenAlex are coded as first, middle or last author (OpenAlex, 2024). This allowed us to count the number of first, middle and last authors by country and by year. We assume that different authorship positions indicate different roles in the creation of knowledge and contribute to different components of the research process (Sauermann & Haeussler, 2017). Last authorship has been found to be related to higher academic ranks and supervision roles, while first authors are more associated with technical work (Larivière et al., 2021). In either case, across scientific fields, authors who hold first or last authorship positions – as opposed to a middle position – are considered to have a primary role in the research (Larivière et al., 2016) and those positions are more highly valued in research evaluation (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2019). Research on authorship contributions in scientific publication does, however, reveal distinct patterns across disciplines. For example, in biomedical fields, work is more highly divided compared to mathematics, physics, and social sciences (Larivière et al., 2016). In this paper we assume that in the case of the field of education, first and last authors are more valued than middle authors positions. We combine first and last authors into a single category of “most valued author position” and categorise middle authors as comprising “less valued author positions”, which does not suggest that middle authors do not make any contribution to the research process.

4. Findings and discussion

4.1 Number of publications in the field of education by authors from Africa

Table 2 shows the publication trends for the period 2000 to 2023. (The data for individual African countries are presented in Annexure A.) Taken together, papers in the field of education authored by at least one researcher from Africa increased from 288 in 2000 to 9,865 papers in 2023 (we limit the period to full years). This is equivalent to a compound average growth rate (CAGR) of 15.86%. In comparison, growth of all papers in education increased from 92,008 to 430,909 for the same period; a CAGR of 6.64%. In other words, the number of publications with a least one author from Africa has increased at a rate that is just over double that of the world growth rate (albeit from a relatively low base). Moreover, the percentage of papers with at least one author from Africa in relation to all papers in the field of education has increased from 0.31% in 2000 to 2.29% in 2023 (Table 2).

Table 2: Number of publications in the field of education, 2000-2023

Year	Africa	World	Africa as % of World
2000	288	92 008	0.31%
2001	378	100 756	0.38%
2002	438	113 828	0.38%
2003	477	123 740	0.39%
2004	694	133 724	0.52%
2005	823	151 667	0.54%
2006	886	171 228	0.52%
2007	867	195 336	0.44%
2008	1 050	219 800	0.48%
2009	1 158	253 725	0.46%
2010	1 513	288 448	0.52%
2011	2 080	322 779	0.64%
2012	2 595	353 280	0.73%
2013	3 643	383 855	0.95%
2014	4 415	406 744	1.09%
2015	4 152	431 125	0.96%
2016	4 612	449 181	1.03%
2017	4 863	468 747	1.04%
2018	5 400	478 023	1.13%
2019	6 569	511 125	1.29%
2020	8 180	525 705	1.56%
2021	9 093	460 586	1.97%
2022	9 218	401 583	2.30%
2023	9 856	430 909	2.29%
TOTAL	83 248	7 467 902	
CAGR	15.86%	6.64%	

The data in Table 2 suggest a positive change in the participation of education researchers from Africa in the global field of education research. Three caveats should, however, be noted.

First, while growth in absolute numbers is a positive indicator of growth in the field of education on the continent, such growth should be compared with the growth of other fields over the same period. Mouton and Blanckenberg (2018), show that Africa's share of world publications was 1.5% in 2005 and rose to 3.2% in 2016. These shares of the world total are higher than those for the field of education shown in Table 2 (0.54% in 2005 and 1.03% in 2016). In a more recent study, Sooryamoorthy (2022) finds that for the period 2001 to 2018,

Africa contributed 7.6% to world science. Based on the data in Table 2, the field of education contributed only 0.79% to education research globally over the same 19-year period. However, there is also a marked increase in the contribution of education research from Africa post-2018 to 1.84%. While Pouris and Ho (2014) categorise education research as an "under-represented research area", more recently, the proportion of education research in relation to world production of articles has been increasing, although it still lags behind overall publication output and, specifically, behind fields such as chemistry, engineering, physics, material sciences, infectious diseases, environmental sciences and ecology and agriculture which all contributed more than 5% to the total number of global publications in their respective fields for the period 2001 to 2018 (Sooryamoorthy, 2022; see also Pouris & Ho, 2014). (Some caution is required when making these comparisons given that Sooryamoorthy (2022), Mouton and Blanckenberg (2018) and Pouris and Ho (2014) all relied on Clarivate Web of Science data, and we rely on data from OpenAlex.)

Second, it should be noted that the data in Tables 2 and A1 (in Annexure A) are not normalised to account for research capacity (i.e., the number of researchers in each country), let alone the number of researchers working in the field of education. The number of publications per researcher in the field of education would make possible comparisons between countries but data on the national scientific workforce for countries in Africa is either only available at the aggregate level, or unavailable or published infrequently (UNESCO, 2024).

Third, while the increase in the contribution of researchers from Africa to the field of education globally is positive in terms of knowledge from Africa contributing to global science, it does not reveal anything about the nature of the collaborations and contributions made by the researchers from Africa. It is to these issue that we next turn our attention.

4.2 Collaboration in the field of education by researchers from Africa

Table 3 and Figure 1a shows that there has been no change in terms of which collaboration types are more prevalent over time. In the field of education, researchers from Africa most often tend not to collaborate – 3,589 out of 9,856 articles (37%) were single authored in 2023. However, when they do collaborate (6,267 or 63% of articles in 2023), it tends to be with colleagues from their own research institution or, less frequently, with international colleagues. Collaboration between researchers at different institutions in the same country (i.e., national collaboration) is the least common type of collaboration. This finding appears to reveal a field effect in collaboration given the findings of Mouton and Blanckenberg (2018) who find no collaboration to be less frequent than national collaboration. (Further comparisons for other collaboration types between our findings and those of Mouton and Blanckenberg [2018] are not possible because the units of analysis are not comparable. Their study effectively treats Africa as a country in their categorisation of international collaboration).

Figure 1a also shows the relative increases in the number of papers over time for all collaboration types. In the case of "no collaboration" there has been a consistent upward trend from 2000 to 2023, with a sharp increase from 2009 onwards. "Institutional collaboration" also shows a steady increase over time, mirroring the trend of "no collaboration" publications, with a similar sharp increase from 2009 onwards. "National collaboration" has the lowest publication counts overall but shows a similar upward trend, with a more gradual increase compared to the other categories. In the case of "international collaboration", Figure 1a shows a steady increase, with a steeper rise from 2011 onwards.

Overall, all categories show an increase in the number of publications over time, with a notable acceleration in the growth rate from 2009 to 2011 onwards, and international and institutional collaborations growing the fastest in more recent years (post-2015). In terms of the change in collaboration over the full period, the compound annual growth rate for each type of collaboration is as follows: no collaboration: 12.90%; institutional collaboration: 19.11%; national collaboration: 23.99%; international collaboration: 18.02%. While there are periodic growth spurts as already noted, over the full period the growth in all forms of collaboration has increased at a greater rate than no collaboration. National collaboration has grown most of the collaboration types; and there is little difference in the CAGR of institutional and international collaboration in the case of education research publications. Notable is that the gap between national collaboration and other collaboration types, including international collaboration, has been widening in more recent times. For the last five years (2018-2023) the CAGR for international collaboration was 13.97% compared with national collaboration at 11.39%. While the relative number of articles by collaboration type have remained consistent over time, there are therefore small differences in the rates at which the different collaboration types are growing.

Table 3: Number of collaborations in the field of education by location of co-authors relative to author from Africa, all Africa, 2000-2023

Year	No collaboration	Institutional collaboration	National collaboration	International collaboration
2000	195	44	6	43
2001	242	64	17	55
2002	293	81	10	54
2003	316	77	22	62
2004	448	142	29	75
2005	516	172	34	101
2006	531	167	46	142
2007	534	164	50	119
2008	599	195	61	195
2009	686	216	63	193
2010	904	286	101	222
2011	1 151	462	133	334
2012	1 434	590	195	376
2013	1 943	963	279	458
2014	2 345	1 144	372	554
2015	2 132	1 054	347	619
2016	2 259	1 202	374	777
2017	2 341	1 314	392	816
2018	2 488	1 446	508	958
2019	2 958	1 808	610	1 193
2020	3 522	2 221	783	1 654
2021	3 621	2 555	930	1 987
2022	3 361	2 714	1 022	2 121
2023	3 589	2 927	1 046	2 294
CAGR	12.90%	19.11%	23.99%	18.02%

Figure 1a: Number of collaborations in the field of education by location of co-authors relative to author from Africa, all Africa, 2000-2023

Figure 1b disaggregates international collaboration into two sub-types: collaboration with authors from so-called core countries (i.e., those with well-resourced national science systems) and collaboration with international authors from so-called periphery countries (i.e., those with less well-resourced national science systems). The data show that collaboration with authors in both core and peripheral countries have increased over time and that, for the first time, collaboration with authors from peripheral countries surpassed collaboration with authors from core countries in 2021.

Figure 1b: Number of international collaborations in the field of education by location of co-authors relative to author from Africa, all Africa, 2000-2023

A detailed and fine-grained analysis of research collaboration as we have defined it in this paper and at the country level is not possible within the scope of this paper. However, a preliminary examination of the collaboration types at the national level comprising the country in each of the four regions of the continent with the highest number of publications (i.e., South Africa, Nigeria, Egypt and Kenya; see Table 1) reveal only minor variations in the growth rates by type of collaboration but the dominance of single authored publications remains, with the exception of Kenya and, to a lesser degree, Egypt. In Kenya institutional collaboration surpassed no collaboration in 2018 while in Egypt international collaboration

eclipsed no collaboration in 2020. Nevertheless, no collaboration remains prominent, if not dominant, in all countries. One intuitive explanation for the growth and dominance of single author publications (i.e. no collaboration) is that South Africa produces significantly more education research than do other countries in Africa; and South Africa has since 2005 had a government-sponsored financial reward system for publications that discourages collaboration (Cloete et al., 2018). But as already indicated, even in the case of education research produced by South African authors, “no collaboration” still accounts for most publications across the full period 2000-2023.

For the four countries selected, national collaboration in the field of education research remains the least frequent type of collaboration, with the exception of Nigeria where international collaboration was less common (although both national collaboration and international collaboration lag well behind no collaboration and institutional collaboration). A possible explanation for Nigerian education research collaboration occurring more frequently at the national level could be a combination of the size of the higher education system (169 universities approved by the National University Commission as of 2020, [Akinnuwesi et al., 2020]) and, more importantly, the number of local journals catering for the publication of education research (Mills et al., 2023). Conversely, the relatively lower number of publications co-authored with international peers could be as a result of the negative perception of the Nigerian higher education and scientific publishing system (Mills et al., 2023).

Based on the publication behaviour of education researchers in Africa, the bibliometric data on the quantum of publications suggest that they tend to work in isolation or, at most, with colleagues from their own institutions. Comparatively, they are not as connected to the scientific core as their peers in other scientific fields (cf. Adams et al., 2014; Mouton & Blanckenberg, 2018; Sooryamoorthy, 2022). This relatively lesser participation is further supported by the data on the growth by collaboration type over time which shows that growth in institutional and national collaboration between researchers in Africa has increased at a greater rate than international collaboration in the case of education research publications, and that international collaboration between researchers from the African continent and peers located in the scientific periphery has surpassed collaboration between researchers in Africa and their peers in more well-resourced (core) national science systems.

The analysis of the data presented in Figures 1a and 1b mask several possible effects which may drive differences at the national level, including national- or institution-level incentives or reward systems, country size, demographics, history, culture and the presence of mega scientific projects, all of which may influence how researchers in Africa collaborate (Adams et al., 2014; Mouton & Blanckenberg, 2018). Such factors and their diversity across African countries have led some scholars to call for “a continuing need to examine the bottom-up factors that explain complex regional and local outcomes departing from the top-down global template” (Adams et al., 2014: 553; Onyanche, 2011).

Whether as a result of field effects (it is more common for education research to single author their publications), the availability of local publication venues (there are several, good local journals for education researchers to publish in), or incentive and reward schemes (there are more incentives and reputational benefits for South-South collaboration), the data on collaboration suggests that researchers from Africa in the field of education typically do not collaborate with peers from the scientific core based on co-authorship as a proxy for collaboration. They either write and publish articles on their own, or they collaborate with

their colleagues in the same institution. If they do collaborate with international peers, they are increasingly doing so with those from countries regarded as peripheral in the global science system. Thus, the “intrusion” of non-local research agendas on Africa education research may be ameliorated by the fact that collaboration patterns are shifting, and by the relatively high numbers of institutionally co-authored papers that are more likely to be sensitive to local or national policy issues.

4.3 Author position of researchers from Africa in the field of education

The category of “Most valued authorship positions” (a combination of first and last author positions) peaked at 86% in 2005 and declined to 67% in 2023 (Figure 2). In other words, in 2023 for publications in the field of education of which at least one author is affiliated to an organisation in Africa, two-thirds of those publications list authors from Africa in the first or last positions. By contrast, middle authors or “less valued author positions” more than doubled from 15% in 2000 to 33% in 2023.

Figure 2: Percentage of authorship position value in the field of education for papers with one author from Africa, 2000-2023

As was the case for contribution types, preliminary analysis was done by country to check for any deviations at that level. The results were similar in that there are no noticeable differences between the aggregated and national-level data. At the country level, the proportion of middle authors was 26% for South Africa, 34% for Nigeria, 36% for Egypt, and 32% for Kenya.

Our analysis rests on the literature which shows that authors who hold first or last authorship positions are considered to have a primary role in the research conducted (Larivière et al., 2016); and on the assumption that in the case of the field of education, first and last authors are also more valued than middle authors positions. The data suggests that educational researchers in Africa are losing their position as primary or substantive contributions of the knowledge they publish. This is consistent with findings from global health research which suggest that collaborating with high-income country researchers decreases local representation, particularly in the first and last author positions (Hedt-Gauthier et al., 2019).

While this may seem to suggest that researchers from Africa are increasingly being marginalised and squeezed into less valued middle-author positions and, as such, this may provide evidence of the marginalisation of peripheral science, there are other effects which

may account for this trend. One likely explanation is that the effect is due to the increasing number of authors per published paper (An et al., 2020; Fortunato et al. 2018); simply put: teams in science are getting bigger. If this is indeed the case, then the number of middle authors will invariably increase because of the limited number of first and last author positions in relation to the number of middle authors. However, in the field of education research in Africa, our data show that there has not been an increase in the number of collaborative authors (Figure 3). The average number of co-authored papers remains relatively stable at three authors per paper for the 20-year period, with an increase from 2019. However, the average number of authors does not at any point exceed an average of 3.55 authors per paper (in 2023), suggesting that the number of authors per paper is unlikely to account for an increase in the relative number of middle authors to first/last authors in the case of education research. This finding is consistent with previous research on differences in co-authorship across disciplines (Lewis et al., 2012) and which found that the average number of papers in the social sciences and in arts and humanities was relatively low compared to other fields, and of the same order of magnitude as the data presented in Figure 3 (Thelwall & Maflahi, 2022).

Figure 3: Average number of authors for co-authored papers with one author from Africa in the field of education, 2000-2023

A second possible explanation for a relative increase in middle authors is the changing demographics of researchers in the field of education in Africa. If the research workforce is becoming younger – mimicking the demographic trends of the continent’s general population (Maassen, 2020) – then it is possible that the relative number of young researchers to more established researchers in Africa has increased over time, and that these younger researchers are more likely to occupy middle author positions that reflect the kinds of research tasks typically assigned to more junior researchers. Mouton et al. (2018) in a large-scale survey of younger researchers in Africa note from their interview data that younger researchers often report being excluded from decision-making when participating in international collaboration. Being disempowered could result in the relegation of these authors to the middle author position, and would impact on our findings if indeed there is an increase in the number of younger researchers on the continent.

5. Limitations

In this paper we provide a description of research collaboration based only on quantitative data. While we believe that providing a data-driven overview of collaboration makes an

important contribution in that it provides a foundation for further analysis, we also believe that follow-up qualitative research would greatly enrich the findings presented in this paper. Without qualitative research it is near-impossible to describe the choices, the motivations behind those choices, and the eventual outcomes of researchers' research designs and publications without conducting surveys or interviews with those very researchers who have authored the papers included in this analysis.

While there is precedent in the field of bibliometrics for using author position to indicate the nature and level of contributions made by authors to published research, it remains a proxy indicator. Once a sufficient body of longitudinal data are available, further research could conduct an analysis using the increasingly accepted practice of indicating author contributions on papers, for example, through the use of the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT, 2024).

We opted to use OpenAlex as a dataset for the reasons outlined in the methods section. However, OpenAlex is still a relatively new dataset and one that is regularly being improved in terms of its quality. Our decision to opt for broader coverage and our preference to work with open datasets comes at the expense of less clean data (Alperin et al., 2024). Any methodological issues of our own doing aside, we do not believe that using different datasets would have produced a more accurate depiction of collaborations in the context of education research in Africa.

6. Conclusion

This paper was informed by several concerns. The first was how researchers in so-called “peripheral countries” navigate the tensions inherent in being locally relevant while simultaneously participating in the global science network. The expectations of external stakeholders are for researchers to manage these competing demands by publishing new knowledge that is both relevant to local needs (and policies) while still contributing to global science. The second was a concern that there is a belief among the same stakeholders that more collaborative research between core and periphery researchers is a panacea for the observed asymmetries between researchers from different countries and regions in the production of scientific knowledge. Researchers from the periphery must have offer something of value to researchers located in core countries should they wish to participate in what is referred to as global science while simultaneously attending to demands for locally relevant, place-based research which may well be undervalued by global science.

We elected to focus on education research in Africa because of the paucity of research on collaboration in this scientific field. Based on the concerns outlined above and our interest in the field of education research in Africa, we asked two questions: How do researchers from Africa in the field of education collaborate? And does the contribution of researchers from Africa in the field of education change over time?

Noting the explanatory limitations of a quantitative approach, we nevertheless adopted a bibliometric analysis of publications by education researchers in Africa to answer the research questions because it allowed us to provide data not published before and our approach allowed us to describe changes over time with respect to research collaboration in this field.

We found that education researchers in Africa tend not to collaborate; instead they are most likely to be sole authors. When they do collaborate, they most often do so with researchers at their own institution or, less frequently, with international peers. National collaboration is the least common type of collaboration in the case of African education research. This hierarchy

of contribution types has remained the same over time, although collaboration at the national level has become relatively less frequent over time.

We further found that when education researchers from Africa collaborate with peers from outside of their country (international collaboration), they are increasingly doing so with those from countries regarded as peripheral in the global science system and this may signal a shift away from the “intrusion” of non-local research agendas on Africa education research. However, when we examined the author position of African education researchers, we found that authors from Africa typically occupy the middle-author position, and the trend shows that they are increasingly occupying this position. This could suggest limited authority or influence over decision-making when collaborating in research with international peers.

Taken together, the findings suggest that researchers from Africa publishing in the field of education are not highly collaborative, and when they do collaborate with peer from the scientific core, their contribution may be limited to less-valued research tasks. As noted, qualitative research as well as further quantitative research is required to provide nuance and further insight into the findings and tentative conclusions presented in this paper. In terms of quantitative research of the type presented in this paper, more fine-grained analysis at the country and institutional levels would be informative. An analysis of the similarities or differences in research themes or topics by collaboration type by country or region would also be informative in terms of providing a deeper understanding of how education researchers align with global discourses and local needs. Finally, as indicated previously in this paper, analysis of contribution statements in the place of author position, could confirm whether education researchers from Africa are being assigned less valued research tasks when they collaborate with international peers.

Finally, we note that several of the underlying concerns of the paper – around equity, agenda-setting and the structures of recognition in global science – have real relevance for research policy, funding and for institutional strategies. For example, large funders of research in Africa, including multinational funders such as the European Union and philanthropic agencies such as the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation – both of which wield significant influence over science funding in Africa – should take more seriously not only who decides what research is funded but also how the research process is governed more equitably. The equitable participation of researchers for Africa in the entire research process – from setting priority research areas, to designing funding instruments, selecting relevant research for funding, and determining who constitutes and takes leadership roles in research teams, should all be more inclusive if shifts are to take in prevailing asymmetries in the production of scientific knowledge. At the institutional level, the ARUA-Guild initiative has placed strong emphasis on approaching collaborative research differently by emphasizing equitable partnerships as central to governance and operation of collaboration research between the participating European and African universities (Maassen, 2020). The outcomes and successes of such initiatives that set out by acknowledging the asymmetries between the scientific core and periphery should be monitored closely, and the outcomes and insights gained be made transparent to generate new models and paradigms for research collaboration across the globe.

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Annexure A

Table A.1: Number of publications per African country per year in the field of education for which at least one author of a scientific publication is affiliated to an organisation in Africa, 2000-2024

	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	total
World	92 008	100 756	113 828	123 740	133 724	151 667	171 228	195 336	219 800	253 725	288 448	322 779	353 280	383 855	406 744	431 125	449 181	468 747	478 023	511 125	525 705	460 586	401 583	430 909	233 414	7 701 316
South Africa	148	206	245	257	409	459	438	457	546	625	794	1044	1227	1608	2111	1744	1980	1690	1665	1837	1956	2398	2489	2683	1599	30615
Nigeria	30	44	48	61	105	119	109	112	137	201	280	408	571	923	969	864	810	984	1194	1581	2094	2135	1753	1928	840	18300
Egypt	9	12	10	12	15	15	26	33	37	30	46	65	89	127	154	205	229	268	323	357	462	588	645	672	363	4792
Kenya	9	8	19	13	12	18	23	26	12	32	43	57	104	149	184	204	220	345	350	410	474	531	563	602	274	4682
Ghana	12	10	13	7	15	30	55	27	48	32	42	63	93	118	140	168	170	200	273	349	496	449	613	590	389	4402
Mozambique	5	6	5	13	12	7	22	17	12	16	15	22	22	40	70	67	114	154	182	287	381	548	438	436	177	3068
Ethiopia	0	2	2	4	5	2	10	8	20	13	15	22	18	36	70	67	91	136	144	255	273	272	354	398	219	2436
Morocco	1	6	6	3	4	6	9	9	12	10	13	20	21	39	79	64	91	114	139	172	247	297	350	443	220	2375
Algeria	11	8	16	26	24	38	40	34	38	34	49	74	60	63	64	107	157	178	148	169	232	263	159	146	78	2216
Tanzania	8	3	6	6	6	14	30	12	14	23	19	51	45	45	59	81	97	115	144	122	186	183	324	325	224	2142
Zimbabwe	12	12	11	6	11	17	15	24	25	12	14	36	75	158	163	138	88	96	123	80	111	145	189	174	78	1813
Uganda	2	3	2	5	6	6	12	13	12	19	16	39	39	44	45	42	66	87	88	119	138	141	206	255	182	1587
Sudan	0	1	3	1	2	1	3	3	5	7	8	19	15	21	22	56	67	81	120	172	216	228	211	246	56	1564
South Sudan	5	7	8	10	7	6	4	2	12	11	7	16	26	19	24	33	58	51	72	86	202	105	125	92	125	1113
Botswana	8	16	16	15	13	31	29	29	37	38	38	41	48	54	47	55	59	49	55	46	47	55	45	51	31	953
Zambia	2	2	4	5	3	4	7	7	12	7	8	10	9	38	35	40	53	41	62	95	112	110	88	120	52	926
Cameroon	6	13	10	10	12	14	18	10	20	8	10	18	25	32	37	34	39	47	64	58	88	82	73	106	50	884
Tunisia	1	5	0	1	6	6	6	8	13	9	18	10	22	48	40	29	63	56	47	69	65	90	76	84	55	827
Angola	2	1	0	2	0	2	0	2	6	3	10	5	19	13	44	29	37	43	33	56	99	110	116	89	27	748
Rwanda	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	1	2	3	5	3	5	1	9	9	16	20	17	29	61	75	129	110	93	591
Namibia	1	2	4	3	1	2	5	1	5	3	8	12	10	18	17	24	45	32	40	50	41	71	61	78	39	573
Sao Tome & Principe	2	1	0	3	3	5	1	7	5	7	6	10	5	9	11	15	16	15	15	17	48	69	52	122	57	501
Malawi	1	4	3	2	5	3	6	2	8	6	6	7	17	17	20	22	31	17	29	32	46	40	57	52	21	454
Benin	0	1	0	3	4	2	1	2	1	1	8	7	12	8	13	19	14	16	18	17	32	39	26	45	10	299
Libya	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	4	4	9	3	12	7	8	17	12	12	17	51	42	51	27	280
Mauritius	1	0	0	0	4	3	6	4	2	3	1	11	5	13	13	18	18	15	10	20	23	21	32	17	11	251
Lesotho	1	1	3	0	0	2	0	1	9	4	11	10	6	12	7	10	13	4	11	14	16	27	27	37	18	244
Guinea-Bissau	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	3	0	2	4	5	3	3	8	17	16	12	36	14	36	38	33	6	241
Eswatini	2	1	1	1	4	1	3	4	2	3	5	3	3	6	6	14	6	6	8	28	28	21	34	22	11	223
Burundi	0	0	1	2	1	3	0	0	2	3	8	5	7	1	6	9	10	10	12	19	11	26	29	25	8	198
Senegal	1	0	0	2	3	0	5	3	3	1	5	4	5	5	1	11	2	6	13	15	19	22	17	15	13	171
Togo	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	4	0	1	0	2	3	7	1	12	11	28	29	39	13	5	161
Ivory Coast	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	3	5	0	2	2	5	5	6	7	10	12	14	16	27	16	12	146
Niger	2	2	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	2	3	7	6	5	8	4	10	8	8	13	7	17	14	3	123
Mali	1	0	2	1	2	3	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	4	5	6	2	3	5	7	9	9	17	21	6	115
Somalia	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	3	0	1	2	2	2	9	2	0	2	2	10	2	3	11	15	24	5	98
Sierra Leone	2	1	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	3	1	3	4	6	6	15	12	16	11	86
Burkina Faso	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	3	0	1	1	2	2	3	3	0	3	9	5	10	9	6	8	1	70
Cabo Verde	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	2	1	4	2	0	6	5	5	5	10	6	5	3	4	61
Madagascar	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	2	1	4	0	3	11	12	6	10	3	57
Liberia	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	1	0	1	1	2	0	0	2	3	1	1	22	2	3	5	5	52
Eritrea	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	1	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	3	3	8	5	5	3	8	46
Gambia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	2	3	5	7	8	8	7	45
Seychelles	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	4	0	3	1	0	13
Mauritania	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	1	3	0	1	12
Gabon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	3	0	10
Guinea	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	3	0	0	0	9
Chad	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	2	8
Central African Republic	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	3
Djibouti	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Equatorial Guinea	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1

Table A.2: Countries with average GERD as a percent of GDP greater than the world average, 2004-2023

Country	Ave GERD % GDP, 2004-2023
Australia	2.07
Austria	2.84
Belgium	2.43
Canada	1.81
China	1.89
Denmark	2.83
Finland	3.18
France	2.18
Germany	2.84
Iceland	2.36
Israel	4.52
Japan	3.22
Korea, Rep.	3.78
Liechtenstein	5.87
Netherlands	1.99
Norway	1.76
Singapore	2.08
Slovenia	1.98
Sweden	3.32
Switzerland	2.97
United Kingdom	2.02
United States	2.86
World	1.69